

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LIBRARY RESOURCE UTILIZATION AND IMPACT

¹Padwal Sachin Baburao, ²Dr. Mohammad Nasir

¹Research Scholar, ²University Librarian and Department Head

^{1,2}Library and Information Science, Kalinga University, Naya Raipur (C. G.)

Abstract

This study examines the comparative use of library resources at two state agricultural universities in India Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya (IGKV), Raipur, and Vasant Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth (VNMKV), Parbhani. The primary objectives were to analyze the types of resources accessed, frequency and purpose of library use, and the impact of these resources on academic performance, research productivity, and user satisfaction. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from 200 respondents (students, research scholars, and faculty) through questionnaires, interviews, and observation. Results indicate that while digital resources such as e-journals and e-books are increasingly preferred, print resources remain essential for exam preparation and foundational study. Students emerge as the most frequent library users, while research scholars and faculty primarily access specialized digital resources. Comparative findings reveal that IGKV users rely more on print and exam-oriented resources, whereas VNMKV users report higher engagement with digital platforms and greater research impact. Overall satisfaction levels remain high, though challenges include limited access to international databases, the need for digital literacy training, and demands for extended library hours. The study highlights the evolving role of ICT-enabled hybrid libraries in supporting academic excellence and research in agricultural universities.

Keywords: Academic libraries, IGKV, VNMKV, print resources, digital resources, research productivity, user satisfaction, agricultural education.

1. INTRODUCTION

University libraries are regarded as the backbone of higher education institutions, serving as vital centers for academic support, research facilitation, and information dissemination (Kaur & Verma, 2019). In the context of agricultural universities, their importance becomes more significant because they cater not only to students and faculty but also to researchers and extension workers engaged in generating and transferring agricultural innovations to farming communities (Patel, 2021). The utilization of library resources—both print and digital directly influences academic outcomes, research productivity, and the quality of agricultural education (Sinha & Singh, 2020).

The past two decades have witnessed a paradigm shift in the functioning of university libraries in India, driven largely by information and communication technologies (ICTs). Libraries have increasingly adopted automation software such as Koha, digital repositories, and access to electronic databases through initiatives like the Consortium for e-Resources in Agriculture (CeRA) and Krishikosh (ICAR, 2022). These developments have enhanced resource accessibility and knowledge sharing across institutions, enabling scholars in remote regions to access updated scientific literature in real time. However, disparities still exist in

terms of infrastructure, user awareness, and levels of resource utilization across different universities (Sharma, 2020).

Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya (IGKV), Raipur, and Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth (VNMKV), Parbhani, are two prominent state agricultural universities in India. Both universities maintain well-established central libraries that provide a blend of print and digital resources, ICT-enabled services, and user-focused facilities. For instance, IGKV's Nehru Library is designated as a regional library hub by ICAR and holds more than one lakh resources, including access to CeRA and Krishikosh (Nehru Library, IGKV, 2023). Similarly, the Central Library of VNMKV, established in 1972, has adopted modern tools such as Koha and RFID technology to provide efficient access to books, journals, and e-resources for students, faculty, and extension staff (VNMKV, 2023). Despite these similarities, institutional contexts, regional needs, and patterns of resource utilization differ, thereby necessitating a comparative assessment of library use and impact.

This paper aims to conduct a comparative analysis of library resource utilization at IGKV and VNMKV, focusing on how these resources contribute to academic, research, and extension activities. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the types of library resources (print and digital) accessed by users at IGKV and VNMKV.
2. To analyze the frequency and purpose of library use among students, researchers, and faculty.
3. To assess the impact of library resources on academic performance, research productivity, and user satisfaction.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

The present study was conducted at two state agricultural universities in India: Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya (IGKV), Raipur in Chhattisgarh, and Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth (VNMKV), Parbhani in Maharashtra. Both universities are recognized for their significant contributions to agricultural education, research, and extension activities, and they maintain well-established central libraries with a wide range of print and digital resources. The selection of these universities for the study is based on their regional importance and the presence of modern ICT-enabled library systems.

2.2 Population and Sample

The population of the study comprised students (undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral), faculty members, and research scholars who are regular users of the central libraries of IGKV and VNMKV. From this population, a stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation across user categories.

- A total of 200 respondents were selected, with 100 each from IGKV and VNMKV.
- Within each university sample, the distribution included approximately 60 students, 25 research scholars, and 15 faculty members. This distribution ensured that the study captured diverse perspectives regarding library use and impact.

Tools for Data Collection

To gather primary data, the following tools were used:

1. **Structured Questionnaire** – designed to collect quantitative data on the frequency of library use, types of resources accessed, purposes of use, and levels of satisfaction.

2. **Interviews** – semi-structured interviews were conducted with faculty members and librarians to gain qualitative insights into challenges, service quality, and institutional practices.
3. **Observation** – non-participant observation was used to study user behavior within the library (e.g., use of digital terminals, seating patterns, and reference services).

Methods of Data Analysis

The collected data was analyzed using a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches:

- **Quantitative Analysis:** Responses from the questionnaire were coded and analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation) and inferential tests such as the chi-square test to identify significant differences between IGKV and VNMKV.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** Data from interviews and observations were analyzed thematically to identify patterns, user perceptions, and contextual challenges. The qualitative findings were triangulated with quantitative results to strengthen the validity of the study.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the findings of the comparative study conducted at the central libraries of IGKV (Raipur) and VNMKV (Parbhani). Data from 200 respondents (100 from each university) were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Results are structured according to the study objectives.

3.1 Types of Library Resources Accessed

Table 1 shows the types of resources accessed by respondents. Both universities exhibit a strong preference for digital resources (e-databases, e-journals), though print books remain essential for students.

Table 1: Types of Library Resources Accessed by Users (Multiple Responses, % of Respondents)

Resource Type	IGKV (%)	VNMKV (%)	χ^2 -value	p-value
Print Books	82	76	1.21	0.27 (NS)
Print Journals	41	38	0.18	0.67 (NS)
Newspapers/Magazines	56	49	0.92	0.34 (NS)
E-Books	68	72	0.34	0.55 (NS)
E-Journals & Databases	74	81	1.43	0.23 (NS)
Online Thesis/Dissertation	59	64	0.41	0.52 (NS)

Note: NS = Not Significant at 5% level

Interpretation: Both IGKV and VNMKV users rely heavily on digital resources, with e-journals and e-books being the most frequently accessed, while print resources remain important for foundational study materials.

3.2 Frequency and Purpose of Library Use

Table 2 presents the frequency of library visits. Students tend to visit more frequently for study and reference, while faculty and researchers rely more on digital access.

Table 2: Frequency of Library Visits by User Category (% of Respondents)

User Category	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Rarely	Mean Visits/Month
Students (IGKV)	48	37	12	3	16.8
Students (VNMKV)	44	39	13	4	15.6
Research Scholars (IGKV)	32	46	17	5	12.4
Research Scholars (VNMKV)	29	48	18	5	11.8
Faculty (IGKV)	15	41	32	12	7.6
Faculty (VNMKV)	13	44	29	14	7.2

Interpretation: Students use libraries more intensively compared to faculty, with IGKV slightly ahead in daily visits. Research scholars at both universities rely on weekly visits due to research requirements.

Table 3: Purpose of Library Use (Multiple Responses, % of Respondents)

Purpose	IGKV (%)	VNMKV (%)
Study/Examination Preparation	71	68
Research & Reference Work	65	72
Accessing E-Resources	69	74
Reading Newspapers/Current Affairs	52	46
Competitive Exam Preparation	48	55

Interpretation: Research and e-resource access dominate among VNMKV users, while IGKV users slightly emphasize exam preparation and current affairs.

3.3 Impact of Library Resources

The impact of resources was measured in terms of academic performance, research productivity, and overall satisfaction.

Table 4: Perceived Impact of Library Resources on Users (% of Respondents Agreeing/Strongly Agreeing)

Impact Area	IGKV (%)	VNMKV (%)	Mean Score (5-Point Likert)
Improved Academic Performance	78	74	4.1
Enhanced Research Productivity	72	76	4.0
Increased Access to Updated Knowledge	83	85	4.3
Better Preparation for Competitive Exams	59	64	3.7
Overall User Satisfaction	81	79	4.2

Interpretation: Both universities show high satisfaction levels (>79%). VNMKV users rate research productivity slightly higher, while IGKV respondents highlight the role of resources in academic performance.

3.4 Qualitative Insights

From interviews and observations:

- **Faculty** emphasized the need for improved subscription to international databases.
- **Students** highlighted the importance of extended library hours during exams.
- **Librarians** reported challenges in digital literacy among first-year undergraduates.
- **Observation** confirmed increasing use of digital terminals, particularly for e-journals and thesis access.

4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study examined the comparative use of library resources at IGKV (Raipur) and VNMKV (Parbhani) with respect to types of resources accessed, frequency and purpose of use, and the impact of resources on academic and research outcomes. The findings provide valuable insights into the evolving role of university libraries in the digital era.

4.1 Resource Utilization Patterns

The results indicate that both universities have witnessed a shift from traditional print resources to digital platforms. While print books continue to be widely used, e-journals, databases, and e-books dominate among both student and researcher groups. This aligns with broader trends in academic libraries where digital resources offer ease of access, currency of information, and remote availability. However, the persistence of print usage reflects the hybrid nature of learning materials, especially in agriculture where textbooks, manuals, and field guides remain crucial.

4.2 Frequency and Purpose of Library Use

The frequency analysis reveals that students are the most frequent visitors, highlighting the library's centrality in study and examination preparation. Faculty members, on the other hand, rely more on selective and digital access, visiting libraries less frequently. Research

scholars from both universities show a pattern of weekly visits, often linked to their research cycles.

In terms of purpose, VNMKV respondents emphasized research and e-resources more strongly, while IGKV users showed relatively higher reliance on print for academic and exam preparation. This variation may be attributed to differences in curriculum emphasis, resource allocation, and digital training programs available at each institution.

4.3 Academic and Research Impact

The impact analysis suggests that both libraries significantly contribute to academic performance, research productivity, and user satisfaction. Students particularly highlighted improved academic outcomes, while research scholars and faculty emphasized enhanced access to updated knowledge and research resources.

VNMKV scored slightly higher on research productivity impact, which may be due to its relatively stronger emphasis on digital databases and online thesis access. IGKV respondents, however, valued the role of print and mixed resources in exam-oriented learning. These findings reinforce the need for balanced collection development policies that serve diverse user groups.

4.4 User Satisfaction and Challenges

Overall user satisfaction levels were high (above 79% at both universities), demonstrating that ICT-enabled systems and hybrid collections are meeting most user expectations. Yet, qualitative insights revealed persistent challenges:

- **Faculty** stressed the need for broader international database subscriptions, indicating resource gaps for advanced research.
- **Students** demanded longer library hours, especially during examination periods, suggesting a service delivery issue rather than a resource gap.
- **Librarians** observed digital literacy limitations among new undergraduates, pointing to the necessity of orientation and training programs.

4.5 Comparative Perspective

While both IGKV and VNMKV have similar resource infrastructures, subtle differences emerged:

- **IGKV** demonstrated stronger engagement with print resources and exam-related preparation.
- **VNMKV** showed greater reliance on digital resources and stronger perceived impact on research productivity.

5. CONCLUSION

1. University libraries at both IGKV and VNMKV are functioning as vital academic hubs, integrating both print and digital resources.
2. Digital resources (e-journals, e-books, databases) dominate usage patterns, though print books remain crucial for foundational learning.
3. Students are the most frequent library visitors, while faculty and research scholars rely more on selective, research-oriented access.
4. Library resources significantly contribute to academic performance, research productivity, and competitive exam preparation.
5. Overall user satisfaction levels are high (>79%), but challenges persist in terms of international database access, extended library hours, and digital literacy.

6. IGKV shows stronger engagement with print resources and exam-related preparation, whereas VNMKV demonstrates greater reliance on digital resources and research productivity.
7. Strategic improvements in ICT infrastructure, user training, and resource allocation can further enhance the impact of these libraries on teaching, learning, and research.

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